

QUIZ**LAST NAME: Macdonald****FIRST NAME: Amanda****PROGRAM CODE: MIPH****COURSE CODE : ACA 401****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert referencesThe author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **Why should you choose American style writing over British style, according to Cleenewerck and Gulma?**
 - Pronunciation, spelling, meaning, hierarchy, cultural differences, and expressions
 - The US has more political, economic, technological, and cultural influence worldwide
 - Pronunciation, spelling, meaning, grammar, syntax, obscenities, terms of expression, and euphemistic, cultural, and politically correct references¹**
 - America is currently the dominant influence on “world English”

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1*, 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 27-35.

2. **What are the formatting rules and considerations when writing academic essays according to Cleenewerck and Gulma?**

- Structured formatting,² plagiarism,³ and literature reviewing⁴**
- Starting the essay, researching the topic, organizing your ideas, writing, referencing, and editing
- Stating the main thesis, staying focused, generalizations, clear writing, assertions, views, and plagiarism
- Use Chicago style over British style

3. **What is the ultimate key to good academic writing, according to Sebranek, Kemper, and Meyer?**

- Voice
- Drafting
- Punctuation⁵**
- Prewriting

4. **What are the five key factors to keep in mind when revising a paper according to Sebranek, Kemper and Meyer?**

- (1) Organization (2) keeping your purpose in mind (3) picturing your audience (4) reading aloud, and (5) sharing your work

² Ibid., 3.

³ Ibid., 5-13.

⁴ Ibid., 17-22.

⁵ Patrick Sebranek, Dave Kemper, Verne Meyer, *Write Source 2000* (Wilmington: Great Source Education Group, 1999), 173.

- (1) Organization (2) voice (3) picturing your audience (4) reading aloud, and (5) sharing your work
- (1) Taking breaks (2) keeping your purpose in mind (3) voice (4) reading aloud, and (5) sharing your work
- (1) Taking breaks (2) keeping your purpose in mind (3) picturing your audience (4) reading aloud, and (5) sharing your work⁶**

5. **What are the five pillars of successful academic writing according to Turabian?**

- (1) Gathering data⁷ (2) planning an argument⁸ (3) drafting⁹ (4) revising¹⁰ and (5) proper citation¹¹**
- (1) Researching (2) planning an argument (3) drafting (4) revising, and (5) proper grammar
- (1) Gathering data (2) planning an argument (3) revising (4) finalizing your writing, and (5) proper grammar
- (1) Creating a story board (2) planning an argument (3) drafting (4) revising, and (5) proper citation

⁶ Ibid., 69.

⁷ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students & Researchers* (The University of Chicago: The University of Chicago, 2013), 24.

⁸ Ibid., 36.

⁹ Ibid., 48.

¹⁰ Ibid., 68.

¹¹ Ibid., 86.

6. **What are the three elements of an argument, according to Turabian?**
- (1) The core (2) testing the claim, and (3) the evidence that supports that claim
 - (1) The core (2) the reasons for accepting it, and (3) the evidence that supports those reasons¹²**
 - (1) The claim (2) the reasons for accepting it, and (3) the hypothesis
 - (1) The core (2) the reasons for accepting it, and (3) drafting
7. **What are the most common writing mistakes when drafting an academic paper, according to Cleenewerck and Gulma?**
- The oversimplification of material until there is no longer a genuine, causal connection between the alleged causes and the actual effect
 - Anthropomorphism in technical writing causing ambiguity
 - Rejecting studies that are inconclusive just because they have no statistically significant differences
 - The misuse of words, simple grammatical issues, irrelevant information, and inadequate proofreading¹³**
8. **When, and according to which writing style, is it not appropriate to reference something, according to Cleenewerck and Gulma?**
- Harvard writing style says that it is not appropriate to reference when using one's own idea, surveys, experiments, theories, arguments, conclusions, research methods, or when using basic common knowledge¹⁴**

¹² Ibid., 37.

¹³ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 4*, 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2020), 6-9.

¹⁴ Ibid., 57.

- Oxford writing style says that it is not appropriate to reference when using an idea found on the internet, experiments, research methods, or when found in an encyclopedia
- Harvard writing style says that it is not appropriate to reference when paraphrasing of a quote, surveys, experiments, theories, arguments, conclusions, research methods, or when using basic common knowledge
- Harvard writing style says that it is not appropriate to reference when using one's own idea, surveys, experiments, theories, arguments, conclusions, research methods, or when referencing a lecture

9. **What are the seven key concepts described in the WHO House Style Guide?**

- (1) Easily confused and troublesome words (2) discriminatory language (3) the WHO spelling list (4) words ending in -ize, -ise, -yse (5) abbreviations (6) member states and associate members of the WHO, and (7) place names
- (1) Easily confused and troublesome words (2) non-discriminatory language (3) the WHO spelling list (4) words ending in -izo, -lysis, -luis (5) abbreviations (6) member states and associate members of the WHO, and (7) place names
- (1) Easily confused and troublesome words (2) non-discriminatory language (3) the WHO spelling list (4) words ending in -ize, -ise, -yse (5) abbreviations (6) member states and associate members of the WHO, and (7) place names**¹⁵
- (1) Easily confused and troublesome words (2) non-discriminatory behaviour (3) the WHO spelling list (4) words ending in -ize, -ise, -yse (5) abbreviations (6) member states and associate members of the WHO, and (7) place names

¹⁵ World Health Organization, *WHO Style Guide* (Geneva: World Health Organization, 2004), iii-iv.

10. **What are the two most important takeaways from reading the WHO House Style?**

- (1) The WHO House Style and (2) member states and associate members of WHO
- (1) Easily confused and troublesome words and (2) non-discriminatory language are some of the key concepts
- (1) Easily confused and troublesome words and (2) the WHO spelling list
- (1) The use of the right names for WHO, it's member states and its partners, and (2) to treat text correctly and consistently¹⁶**

¹⁶ World Health Organization, *WHO Style Guide*, Second. (Geneva: World Health Organization, 2013), 1.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Gulma, Kabiru. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1*. 2nd ed. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. 8th ed. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2013.

Sebranek, Patrick, Kemper, Dave, and Meyer, Verne. *Write Source 2000*. Wilmington: Great Source Education Group, 1999.

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Gulma, Kabiru. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 4*. 2nd ed. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2020.

WHO, *WHO Style Guide*. Geneva: World Health Organization, 2004.

WHO, *WHO Style Guide*. Second. Geneva: World Health Organization, 2013.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.